

Influence of Politics of Governance on Management of Coronavirus in Nigeria

Samuel Adedayo MUYIWA

*The Polytechnic, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria
muyiwa.adedayo@polyibadan.edu.ng*

ABSTRACT: This paper examines influence of good governance on coronavirus pandemic in Nigeria. The kernel of this article is the intrinsic nexus between good governance, bad governance and coronavirus pandemic in a democratic state. Multi-stage sampling procedure was employed in selecting respondents for the study. 209 of 230 respondents used for the study filled the questionnaire appropriately for the study. The finding of the study shows that there was a positive significant relationship between governance and health information ($r = .581^{**}$, $N= 219$, $P < .05$); citizen and good governance ($r = .485^{**}$, $N= 219$, $P < .05$) and good governance and the management of Coronavirus pandemic ($r = .431^{**}$, $N= 219$, $P < .05$). It therefore shows that there is a need for Government to gain trust among the populace in order to build a policy that will enhance and promote the mitigation of Coronavirus pandemic in Nigeria.

KEYWORDS: Politics, Governance, Good Governance, Coronavirus, Pandemic

Introduction

Governance is the strategic task of setting the organisation's goals, direction, limitations and accountability frameworks. Good governance is essential for community to achieve its objectives and drive improvement, as well as maintain legal and ethical standing in the eyes of populace, organisations, and the wider community. It increases public engagement in managing risks and promoting neighbourhood security, increases likelihood of all income groups surviving disasters; reduces crime rates. Reduces environmental and health impacts of disasters caused by human actions; increases environmental security. Government has an important role to play in the management of health issue of the populace. Governance is assigned the role of provide and assuring an adequate health infrastructure, promotes healthy communities and healthy behaviors, preventing the spread of communicable disease, protecting against environmental health hazards, preparing for and responding to emergencies, and assuring health services which include the current pandemic around the world.

In December 2019, a novel strain of coronavirus—SARS-CoV-2—was first detected in Wuhan, a city in China's Hubei province with a population of 11 million, after an outbreak of pneumonia without an obvious cause. The virus has now spread to over 200 countries and territories across the globe, and it is been characterized as a pandemic by the World Health Organization (WHO) on 11 March 2020 due to the rapid increase in the number of cases outside China which has affected a growing number of countries around the world. This pandemic has cast a new light on the role that government plays in keeping citizenry healthy which implies that stable and effective government must be crucial to managing the coronavirus pandemic.

Coronavirus pandemic calls for government investment in promoting healthy communities and healthy behaviours means activities that improve health in a population, such as engaging communities to change policy, systems or environments to promote positive health or prevent adverse health; providing information and education about healthy communities or population health status; and addressing issues of health equity, health disparities, and the social determinants of health as early prevention is essential in preventing and managing the disease. Managing such crises and addressing their socio-economic consequences requires audacious policy action to maintain functioning healthcare systems, guarantee the continuity of education, preserve businesses and jobs, and maintain the stability of financial markets. Political leadership at the centre is essential to sustain the complex political, social and economic balance of adopting containment measures to reduce the impact of the pandemic while ensuring the provision of essential services. Such leadership is essential for maintaining citizens' trust in government.

Ozili (2020) submitted that some Nigerians have misconceptions about COVID-19, they believe it is a biological weapon of the Chinese government, many considered the pandemic as a hoax, some describes it as a 'rich man's disease', while others see it as another conspiracy by politicians to loot the treasury. These misconceptions prevented them from taking maximum preventive measures not even when the government is at centre of making policy about it. Hence, there is a need for evidence-based campaign which should be intensified to remove misconceptions and promote precautionary measures by government. Nigerian populace believes that government has ignored and abandoned, now this government needs the populace whom their needs has largely been ignored for decades.

The neglect and abandonment also reflected in the palliative measures being rolled out during the lockdown when citizens were asked to stay in their homes and businesses and offices closed, while national and international borders remain closed. Eranga (2020) submitted that to alleviate the effects of the lockdown, the Federal Government of Nigeria rolled out palliative measures for targeted groups and lamentations have trailed the distribution of government palliatives by the masses. Citizens alleged that the process of distribution of palliatives had been politicized, although the Federal Government claimed that the palliative is for vulnerable. The salient question is what parameters are been adopted in determining the vulnerable or who are these vulnerable people?

Based on this, to what extent will the populace trust their governments that failed to meet the needs of society while making the use of their resources, government that lack transparency, integrity, lawfulness, sound policy, participation, accountability, responsiveness, and the absence of corruption and wrongdoing in the management and prevention of this pandemic? It is on this basis that this study examines the influence of good and bad governance on the management and prevention of the coronavirus pandemic in Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

- To examine the relationship between governance and Health Information in Nigeria
- To examine the relationship between citizen and good governance in Nigeria
- To examine the relationship between good governance and the management of coronavirus pandemic

Literature Review

Good Governance

The need to protect and ensure life and survivability brought about the state and this can only be achieved by good governance. Different meanings of good governance exist, the term is generally associated with political, economic and social goals that are deemed necessary for achieving development. Hence, good governance is the process whereby public institutions conduct public affairs and manage public resources in a manner that promotes the rule of law and the realization of human rights (civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights). Good governance is considered key to achieving sustainable development and human well-being.

Good governance becomes very fundamental and imperative when viewed against the backdrop of massive deterioration of government institutions, pervasive poverty and alarming unemployment rate, corruption, as well as near total collapse of moral and ethical standards engendered by nearly three decades of military rule in the country, which saw governance capacity weakened at all levels (World Bank 2004; Ujomu 2004).

In 1996, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) declared that "promoting good governance in all its aspects, including by ensuring the rule of law, improving the efficiency and accountability of the public sector and tackling corruption, [are] essential elements of a framework within which economies can prosper." Today, the term good governance is commonly used by national and international development organizations. However, its meaning and scope are not always clear. While this flexibility enables a contextual application of the term, the lack of conceptual clarity can be a source of difficulty at the operational level. In some cases, good governance has become a "one-size-fits-all buzzword" lacking specific meaning and content (Johnston 2002, 7).

Johnston (2002 1-2) defines good governance as "legitimate, accountable, and effective ways of obtaining and using public power and resources in the pursuit of widely accepted social goals". This definition links good governance with the rule of law, transparency and accountability, and embodies partnerships between state and society, and among citizens. Similarly, Rose-Ackerman (2016, 1) suggests that good governance refers to "all kinds of institutional structures that promote both good substantive outcomes and public legitimacy". Good government is also associated with impartiality (Rothstein and Varraich 2017), ethical universalism (Mungiu-Pippidi 2015) and open-access orders (North, Wallis and Weingast, 2009).

State of Coronavirus Pandemic in Nigeria

The novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) has become an important health threat ravaging the entire world with numerous health and economic implications. Nigeria is also among the vulnerable African nations, given the weak state of the healthcare system (Marbot 2020). The pandemic shocked the world, overwhelming the health systems of even high-income countries. Predictably, the situation has elicited social and medical responses from the public and governments, respectively. Nigeria recorded an imported case from Italy on February 27, 2020.

The virus, SARS Cov2 is the main causative organism of COVID-19, with shortness of breath, dry cough and fever as its most common symptoms. The disease is basically transmitted from person to person through contact with droplet of an infected person. Although most people can easily recover from the illness without specialized treatment, people who are older and those with existing medical conditions such as

cancer, chronic respiratory infections, diabetes and cardiovascular diseases are more likely to experience severe illness and death due to COVID-19.

Since the outbreak of COVID-19, numerous preventive and control measures have been applied globally to contain the disease but it is ordinarily difficult to prevent and control. The best way of thwarting it is by adopting measures that will reduce exposure to the virus that causes the disease. This therefore makes the government and political leaders at the centre of management and control of this disease. Research according to (Amzat, Aminu, Kolo, Akinyele, Ogundairo, and Danjibo 2020) submitted that the pre-COVID-19 preparedness was grossly inadequate.

This therefore correspond with the submission that many health experts projected that Africa would face a hard time and struggle to keep the coronavirus outbreak under control once it is confirmed on the continent. The concerns were based on pervasive poverty, weak healthcare systems, and the diseases ravaging most parts of Africa Nigeria inclusive. Although, the Nigerian Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) submitted that the training of the rapid response teams across the 36 states in Nigeria was concluded in December 2019. On January 28, the NCDC further revealed that a Coronavirus Group had been set up to activate its incident system to respond to any emergency. Additionally, the NCDC worked with 22 states in Nigeria to activate their emergency operations centers to manage and link up with the national incidence coordination centers (Ihekweazu 2020). Although the government had strengthened the surveillance at the airport since January 2020, Nigeria recorded its COVID-19 index case that was imported from Italy, on February 27. This raised concerns about the effectiveness of airport surveillance and, by extension, the country's general preparedness. The index case (an Italian) had visited some other states of the federation before testing positive for COVID-19.

Among other measures taking to manage the pandemic is testing and isolation of confirmed positive cases, sensitization of the masses on COVID-19 as well as ways of preventing the disease, using all sources of information, including the radio, television, print and social media. People were also encouraged to regularly wash their hands using sanitizers, use of face mask in public and good reparatory hygiene. In order to ensure complete compliance on the directives on lockdown, social distancing, use of face masks and sanitizers, different state governments constituted taskforces to ensure that people in their respective states do not default. Despites all these measures been put in place there is still steady increase in number of cases as well as number of affected states most especially with this second phase. This therefore support of the submission of Amzat, et al that these plans are grossly inadequate which may result from non-compliant. This is the reason why the Federal Government of Nigeria signed the bill on the use of facemask into law. Although, the studies of (Ibekwe 2020, Mac-Leva et al. 2020) also submitted that the existing health facilities and equipment (including ventilators and PPE) in Nigeria are grossly inadequate to handle the medical emergency due to COVID-19.

Good or bad governance and Management of Coronavirus Pandemic in Nigeria

The importance of good governance as a critical condition for human development can no longer be under estimated. Since the late 1980s, governance has been a subject of considerable debates and different interpretations by governments, international organizations and scholars. Managing and mitigating the effect of coronavirus pandemic depend on the state building trust with its citizens through effective communication and action which can only be achieved by good governance and not bad governance. Good Governance is an approach to government committed to creating a system that protects

human rights and civil liberties while bad governance is negative consequence of this been defined by corruption in Nigerian society.

The concepts of corruption and good governance have a two-way causal relationship with each other and feed off each other in a vicious circle. If good governance principles and structures are not in place, this provides greater opportunity for corruption. Corruption, in turn, can prevent good governance principles and structures from being put in place, or enforced. Violations of the principles of transparency, accountability and rule of law appear to be most closely associated with corruption. Evidence from literature emphasized the importance of principles of transparency and account on dissemination of information on coronavirus pandemic by government. Olagoke, Olagoke, and Hughes (2020) submitted that the public's trust in the government's risk communication and social persuasion strategies may affect their perception of the pandemic's severity, their vulnerability to the virus and their perceived self-efficacy in practicing preventive behavior or taking care of their health. This therefore shows that corruption and poor governance are not only security challenges which undermine democracy, the rule of law and economic development but health challenges.

Hetherington (2005) argues that lower levels of trust undermine the capacity of government to pursue redistributive policies and Marien and Hooghe (2011) that trust increases law compliance. Ineffective institutions undermine the provision of public services such as health care, education and law enforcement. Looting of Covid-19 aids is an example of distrust on governance in Nigeria where the State governors have said the items looted were kept for vulnerable members of society and in preparation for a possible second wave of coronavirus infections. The salient question needs to be raised is this, how many Nigerians benefitted from the initial distribution of the palliative? What measure are been considered in distributing the palliative for the so-called vulnerable by the government? Who are the vulnerable when people when restriction have exposed Nigerian to the problem of hunger? This shows that is an injustice in the distribution of the palliative and this compound the level of distrust of government by the populace. Ghosh and Siddique (2015) and Rose-Ackerman (2016) submitted that good governance, in contrast to democratization, has strong positive effects on measures of social trust, life satisfaction, peace and political legitimacy.

Figure 1. Nigerians looting Covid-19 Aids

Ott (2010) submitted that good governance improves life evaluations either directly, because people are happier living in a context of good government (Ott 2010), or indirectly because good governance enables people to achieve higher levels of something else that is directly important to their well-being. This therefore correspond with the submission of (Van Bavel et al. 2020) on Coronavirus pandemic that greater trust in government leads to more compliance with health policies – such as measures relating to quarantining, testing and restrictions on mass gatherings. The absence of corruption will increase the trust of the populace on government and this increase the efficiency and thus create favourable conditions for on the management of pandemic. There is also evidence that the higher levels of general and specific trust increase the happiness of people even beyond higher incomes (Mungiu-Pippidi 2015). For instance, Helliwell and others (2014) found that changes in government services delivery quality contribute positively to citizens' life evaluation.

Governance is politics and is, therefore, a crucial determinant of the allocation of resources, especially public goods, within a country. Good governance exists where there is responsiveness, equity and consistency in the way resources are allocated to the needs especially those of the poor people. It also affects the quality of decision-making more generally, for instance, those determining economic and social policy. If governance is weak and democratic accountability is poor, then resources are more likely to be appropriated by specific interest groups that may exclude the poor and the resulting policies would be unlikely to reflect the national interest or pro-poor imperatives.

A democratic government is more responsive to the needs of the population such as in providing opportunities in education, health and social welfare, better housing, equitable distribution of development projects including roads and other infrastructural development but democracy in Nigeria is witnessing oppose. Such physical projects taken to local communities and different regions usually provide some employment opportunities even though some may be temporary and business opportunities which enhance people's quality of live. Good governance is one of the essential preconditions for development and promote healthy live for the populace. Such policy measures tend to generally improve people's capabilities as with better education and health they are often able to experience progression in the social structure better than was possible during their parents' generation.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The target population for this study comprised all members of adult population living in Ibadan North local government area of Oyo state, Nigeria. Purposive sampling was employed in selecting Ibadan North Local Government. A simple random sampling technique was employed in selected 230 respondents used for the study. An instrument tagged: Politics, Governance and Management of Coronavirus Pandemic Questionnaire (POGOMOP) was used to collect data for the study. The instrument was made up of two sections. Section A: demographic information of respondents while section B was used to elicit information from the respondents. The reliability of the instrument was determined through a test-retest method within an interval of two weeks to a group of twenty respondents in a Akinyele Local Government Area of Oyo State. Thereafter, Cronbach alpha was used to establish its level of reliability which was computed to be 0.76. Inferential statistics was employed to analyze data collected for the study.

Discussion of Findings

Research Question One: To what extent does governance affects the health information of the populace in Nigeria?

Table I. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Showing the Relationship between governance affects the health information of the populace in Nigeria

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	Remark
Governance	22.1013	3.3167	219	.581**	.000	Sig.
Health Information	20.4316	4.2506				

** Sig. at .05level

It is shown in the above table that there was a positive significant relationship between governance and health information ($r = .581^{**}$, $N = 219$, $P < .05$). Null hypothesis is therefore rejected. Hence, there is a need for government from lower tier (local government) to the highest (Federal Government) to promote equity and equality, justice, transparency and accountability among the populace

Research Question two: Is there any relationship between citizen and good governance in Nigeria?

Table II. Pearson Product Moment Correlation showing the Relationship between Parental citizen and good governance in Nigeria

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	r	P	Remark
Good Governance	10.3550	2.3659	219	.485**	.001	Sig.
Good Citizenry	20.1116	3.0567				

** Sig. at .05 level

It is shown in the above table that there was a positive significant relationship between citizen and good governance ($r = .485^{**}$, $N = 219$, $P < .05$). Null hypothesis is therefore rejected. Hence, government must promote the elements of good governance in order to have a good citizenry.

Research Question three: To what extent does good governance affect the management of Coronavirus pandemic?

Table 14. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Showing the Relationship Between good governance and the management of Coronavirus pandemic

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	r	P	Remark
Good Governance	30.4135	5.2520	219	.431**	.000	Sig.
Management of Coronavirus Pandemic	21.3706	3.0569				

** Sig. at .05 level

It is shown in the above table that there was a positive significant relationship between good governance and the management of Coronavirus pandemic ($r = .431^{**}$, $N = 219$, $P < .05$). Null hypothesis is therefore rejected. Hence, Governance from all arms most especially at the local government level should take into cognizance, the elements of good governance in order to gain more trust among the populace most especially on the management of coronavirus pandemic.

The findings of this study revealed that not only governance that can promote the management of coronavirus pandemic in Nigeria but a governance with transparency, integrity, lawfulness, sound policy, participation, accountability and responsiveness. The study of (Olagoke, Olagoke, & Hughes 2020) corroborate the findings of this study that public's trust in the government's risk communication and social persuasion strategies may affect their perception of the pandemic's severity, their vulnerability to the virus and their perceived self-efficacy in practicing preventive behavior or taking care of their health. In the same vein, Ott (2010) submitted that good governance improves life evaluations either directly, because people are happier living in a context of good government, or indirectly because good governance enables people to achieve higher levels of something else that is directly important to their well-being.

The finding of the study also reveals that there is a need for government to increase their level of transparency and accountability among the populace in order to increase trust. The submission of (Ozili 2020) corroborate the findings of this study where it was submitted that some Nigerians have misconceptions about COVID-19, they believe it is a biological weapon of the Chinese government, many considered the pandemic as a hoax, some describes it as a 'rich man's disease', while others see it as another conspiracy by politicians to loot the treasury. This is an evident that there is lack of trust and accountability between the government and Nigerian populace because Nigerian government has abandoned Nigerian populace and their needs has largely been ignored for decades. In the same vein, the submission of (Eranga 2020) submitted that palliative rolled out by the Federal Government of Nigeria brings about lamentation. Although the Federal Government claimed that the palliative is for vulnerable but who are the these vulnerable, what measures are been adopted in determining the vulnerable people? Citizens therefore alleged the government that the process of distribution of palliatives was politicized.

The finding of the study also shows that government has a greater role to play in the management of coronavirus pandemic. The finding of this study is therefore in line with the submission of (Ibekwe 2020) that there is need for Nigeria government to provide adequate health facilities because the existing health facilities and equipment (including ventilators and PPE) in Nigeria are grossly inadequate to handle the medical emergency due to COVID-19.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The effect of COVID-19 pandemic is been felt in spread in almost all countries and it has affected millions of people around the world and it also resulted in death of million of people as well. This shows that COVID-19 does not recognize borders, hence, governments around the world most especially in developing countries should respond to its management immediately. Although, not all countries, particularly in the developing world, have the right specialists, not all have experts in pandemics, manufacturers can produce the necessary equipment or labs that can develop a vaccine but a good governance must be able to guide and formulate policies to protect citizenry. Governance in Nigeria as a process has impacted negatively on the Nigerian populace and this is affecting them in the management of the pandemic. This is because of the dreaded disease that seems to always inflict its leadership. This disease is called corruption, combined with primitive accumulation of wealth.

This study therefore concludes that governance as well as Political Leaders in Nigeria need to win trust in order to management and mitigate the effect of COVID-19 in the country. They should promote the core element of good governance which are participatory; consistent with the rule of law; transparent; responsive; consensus-

oriented; equitable and inclusive; effective and efficient; and accountable to the citizenry. This will therefore makes them to be agile enough to disregard old norms and move quickly to do everything they can to save lives and support infrastructure and the fabric of society.

On the basis of findings, the following policy recommendations are suggested for managing and mitigating coronavirus pandemic in Nigeria.

- i. That good governance brings about trust and communication is the key to managing corona virus — it is not enough to just decide on a strategy. Being able to communicate it clearly to the public and to the people without fear of distrust from local government to police and the border patrol.
- ii. Governments must be prepared to think outside the box and rescue packages must be put in place through participatory approach. Regulations that are prudent in normal circumstances must be appropriately relaxed to help the national effort.
- iii. Through consensus-oriented, all governments must realize that we live in a globalized world and a crisis like this needs a global response. Cooperation is key. Past tensions must be set aside and countries must work together to help each other meet shortfalls in medicine and equipment.
- iv. Through transparency and responsiveness, stakeholders should be relied on to help with distribution and supporting the populace. Many charities will struggle during this time and need their own levels of support to help them stay afloat and provide vital support where governments cannot.
- v. Government should always be fair in their dealing with the populace to gain more trust and been able to provide a policy that will be generally acceptable by the populace
- vi. Finally, there is also the need for government to communicate the populace through traditional and religious leaders in Nigeria.

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References

- Amzat, J. Aminu, K., Kolo, V. I., Akinyele, A. A., Ogundairo, J. A. and Danjibo, M. C. 2020. "Coronavirus outbreak in Nigeria: Burden and socio-medical response during the first 100 days." *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* 98: 218-224, September 2020.
- Douglass C. North, John Joseph Wallis, and Barry R. Weingast. 2009. "Violence and the rise of open-access orders." *Journal of Democracy Volume* 20 (1):55-68. National Endowment for Democracy and The Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Eranga, I. O. 2020. "COVID-19 Pandemic in Nigeria: Palliative Measures and the Politics of Vulnerability." *Int J MCH AIDS* 9(2): 220–222.
- Fadakinte, M. M. 2013. "Civil Society, Democracy and Good Governance in Nigeria: (1999-2012)." *International Journal of Modern Social Sciences* 2(2): 133-154.
- Fadakinte, M. M. 2015. "State and Society in Africa: An Exploration of African Development Crisis." *Scottish Journal of Arts, Social Sciences and Scientific Studies* 25(1):3-19.
- Ghosh, R. N and Siddique, M. A. B. 2015. "Conclusion: Good Governance and Sustainable Development." World Scientific Book Chapters, in: R N Ghosh & M A B Siddique (ed.), *Corruption, Good Governance and Economic Development Contemporary Analysis and Case Studies*, chapter 12, pages 259-264, World Scientific Publishing Co. Pte. Ltd.

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- Hayo, B. 2006. "Happiness in transition: An empirical study on Eastern Europe." *Economic Systems* 31: 204-221.
- Helliwell, J. F., Huang, H., & Wang, S. 2014. "Social capital and well-being in times of crisis." *Journal of Happiness Studies: An Interdisciplinary Forum on Subjective Well-Being* 15(1): 145-162.
- Hetherington, MJ. 2005. *Declining Political Trust and the Demise of American Liberalism*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Heyman, S. J. 2014. *The conservative-libertarian turn in first amendment jurisprudence*. The third annual C. Edwin Baker lecture for liberty, equality, and democracy. West Virginia Law Review, 117.
- Ibekwe, Titus Sunday and Fasunla, Ayotunde James. 2020. "Telemedicine in otorhinolaryngological practice during COVID-19 pandemic." *Niger Med J* 61:111-3
- Ihekweazu, C. 2020. "Steps Nigeria is taking to Prepare for Cases of Coronavirus." *The Conversation*. <http://theconversation.com/steps-nigeria-is-taking-to-prepare-for-cases-of-coronavirus-130704>.
- Johnston, Michael 2002. "Building a Clean Machine: Anti-Corruption Coalitions and Sustainable Reforms." World Bank Institute Working Paper number 37208 (December).
- Leke, O. 2010. "Democracy and Governance in Nigeria's Fourth Republic." *African Research Review: An International Multi-Disciplinary Journal Ethiopia*, 4(3a).
- Mac-Leva, F. Akor O., S. Echewofun, P. Moses, A.A. Musa, T. Ibrahim, V. Sorokwu, K.R. Anwar, I. Adebayo, B. Willie, H.U. Aminu, R. Ramoni, I.H. Muhammad, U. Abubakar, I.B. Saleh, H.A. Emmanuel, A.M. Hamagam, H. Ibrahim, L. Sadiq, H.G. Yaya. 2020. "COVID-19: Only 169 Ventilators in 16 States." *Daily Trust*. <https://www.dailytrust.com.ng/covid-19-only-169-ventilators-in-16-states.html>.
- Marbot, O. 2020. "Coronavirus Africa Map: Which Countries are Most at Risk?" *The Africa Report*. <https://www.theafricareport.com/23948/coronavirus-africa-which-countries-are-most-at-risk/>.
- Marien, S, Hooghe, M. 2011. "Does Political Trust Matter? An Empirical Investigation into the Relation between Political Trust and Support for Law Compliance." *European Journal of Political Research* 50 (2): 267-291.
- Mato, K. 2005. "Developing Viable Democratic Culture Through the Electoral Process." In Dauda, S., & Liman, A. (ed): *Issues in Nigeria's Political and Economic Development*. Zumuta Publishers, Abuja.
- Mungiu, P. A. 2006. "Corruption: Diagnosis and Treatment." *Journal of Democracy*, July, 17(3). <https://doi.org/10.1353/jod.2006.0050>.
- Mungiu-Pippidi, Alina. 2015. "The quest for good governance: How societies develop control of corruption." Work Package: WP3, Corruption and governance improvement in global and continental perspectives. European Commission within the Seventh Framework Program.
- Oke, L. 2005. "Globalization, Democracy and Women Empowerment: Issues and Challenges in Nigeria." In Olufayo, O. O. (ed): *Perspective on Globalization and African Development*, Lagos: Badagry Publications.
- Olagoke, A. A., Olagoke, O. O. and Hughes, A. M. 2020. "Psychological Pathways Linking Public Trust During the Coronavirus Pandemic to Mental and Physical Well-being." *Front. Psychol.*, 11 November 2020 | <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.570216>.
- Ott, J. 2010. "Good Governance and Happiness in Nations: Technical Quality Precedes Democracy and Quality Beats Size." *Journal of Happiness Studies* 11(3):353-368. DOI:10.1007/s10902-009-9144-7.
- Ozili, P.K. 2020. "COVID-19 Pandemic and Economic Crisis: The Nigerian Experience and Structural Causes." *SSRN Electronic Journal*. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340439471_COVID-19_Pandemic_and_Economic_Crisis_The_Nigerian_Experience_and_Structural_Causes [accessed Feb 04 2021].
- Rodriguez-Pose and Maslaukaite. 2011. "Can policy make us happier? Individual characteristics, socio-economic factors and life satisfaction in Central and Eastern Europe." *Cambridge Journal of Regions, Economy and Society* 5(1): 77-96.
- Rose-Ackerman, Susan. 2016. *Corruption and Government*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Rothstein, Bo and Jan Teorell. 2008. "What Is Quality of Government? A Theory of Impartial Government Institutions." *An UInternational Journal of Policy, administraton and Institutins* 21(2):165-190.
- Rothstein, Bo and Varraich, Aiysha. 2017. *Making Sense of Corruption*. Cambridge University Press.
- Sawyer, A. 2004. "Governance and Democratization." In Adebajo, A., & Rashid, I. (ed) *West Africa's Security Challenges: Building Peace in a Trouble Region*. Colorado, USA: Lynne Rienner Publishers.
- Ujomu, P. O. 2004. "Development Institutions Participation and the Problems of Social Engineering in an African Nation-State." In Ajayi, K. and Ayodele, B. (eds): *Perspectives on Democracy and Development in post-military Nigeria*. Ibadan, Julius and Julius Associates.
- Van Bavel, Jay J, Paulo Boggio, CapraroValerio, Robb Willer...et al. 2020. "Using social and behavioural science to support COVID-19 pandemic response." *Nature Human Behaviour* 4 (5): 460-471.
- World Bank. 2002. "Memorandum of the president of the International Development Association and the Executive Director on an Inter-Strategy update for the Federal Republic of Nigeria." Report No. 2363.